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MAIN ERRORS IN TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses some of the common problems that arise in translation studies. It also highlights the current demand for translation studies and its place in society.

Keywords: text, translation, vocabulary, terminology, translation problems, transformation, information.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the pace of modern globalization and intercultural relations development, the expansion of international relations, the development of trade-economic and financial relations between countries, the strengthening of the process of integration of European countries and the whole world, the development of science and technology, and the continuous exchange of scientific and technical information as effective factors the importance of foreign languages deserves great attention. Also, at the stage of economic, scientific, technical and cultural development, a foreign language is used as a means of oral and written communication between representatives of different peoples of the world.

As a result of the rapid development of knowledge and technologies, translators-specialists who have practical skills in translating scientific and technical texts related to various fields are special today, covering all aspects of modern society and modern economy. worthy of the need. Therefore, the need for highly skilled translators is increasing day by day.

Due to the development of modern technologies, today scientists from different countries of the world have the opportunity to quickly exchange information and conduct joint research, and thanks to these means of communication, unprecedented results are being achieved in modern science. In such conditions, the need for high-quality translation of scientific literature is significantly increasing in many production organizations. Translators must constantly add translations of scientific literature to their vocabulary, increase their ability to understand terms and know their meaning.

Therefore, the translator is the first to translate scientific and technical terms it is necessary to pay great attention to the meaning from the scientific and technical point of view, and then to have the ability to compare with narrow scientific and technical terms.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the process of translation of scientific and technical texts, the following requirements should be followed: translation equivalence, translation accuracy, quality of translation data, logicity of translation and quality of its coverage. In order for a scientific and technical text to have a quality translation, the translator must have the following knowledge and skills:

- Must have knowledge of foreign language theory, phonetics, lexicon and grammatical structure;
- The translation of scientific and technical texts to the practice of special skills;

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-Linguistic practical knowledge (translation methods, transformation, the ability to replace the equivalent of words, the ability to add words, the ability to describe with terms, etc.);

-In the process of translating the text, it is necessary to have extralinguistic knowledge and the ability to use the content of sentences and sentences (in this case, it was required to have sufficient information in translating a special scientific-technical text)

One of the main unknown problems in translation is that the translator does not have a complete understanding of what "scientific translation" is. In order to successfully perform scientific translation, the translator must have an idea of how it differs from other types of translation. In general, the translation of the scientific method includes many texts related to the research topic - starting from theses, it includes abstracts and article reviews, diplomas, dissertations and monograph manuscripts.

When translating the above types of work, attention should be paid to the following factors: the purpose of translation, the method of translation, the organization of the text in the translation and the interrelationships between its parts. In addition to the external structure of academic texts (chapters, sections, paragraphs), there is also its internal structure. The translation of scientific texts has its own characteristics - it is a method of identifying material problems from general information and presenting their solutions. For example, in English, there are a number of words and phrases that are used for different purposes, to connect parts of the text, as well as to move from the meaning of one phrase to another. For example:

- shunga qaramsdan (although, however, despite, in spite of, nevertheless...);
- boshqa so'zlar bilan ifodalaganda (in other words);
- misol uchun (for example, for instance...)
- shuningdek (in addition, moreover, furthermore...);

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Terminological problems in translation.

One of the leading forms of scientific thinking is understanding and perception is related to the concepts of achievement. Almost every term in a scientific text is a lexical unit, and it expresses one of the meanings of special lexical units. These lexical units belong to the category of terms.

In general, a term is a word or phrase that is specific to a certain field in the field of science and technology. The term has clear semantic boundaries in linguistics. It follows that terms are a system of concepts reinforced by verbal expressions related to a particular subject. If a word in common language (except for a term) has many meanings, but it falls into the category of terms, this word will have a specific meaning, and its meaning in the term is used in the translation.

Therefore, one of the main mistakes that a translator makes when translating a scientific text is that he does not have enough skills to use scientific dictionaries or does not have a clear knowledge of the subject specific to the term - this situation is even his own. can also be observed in the mother tongue. In terms of application and quantity, special dictionaries of terms are more widely used in scientific method texts than other types of dictionaries. They are: nomenclature names, professional vocabulary and terms, professional jargon, etc. This lexicon is widely used in all areas of scientific text (that is, text classification, text structure and its function, text components and factors are also taken into account). On average, terminological or terminological vocabulary makes up 20 percent of the total vocabulary of scientific texts.

Grammatical errors in translation.

The style of scientific communication has its own grammatical features. For example, when some texts are translated from English to Uzbek, in some cases the lexical meaning is lost and the verbs have an abstract meaning. For example:

- It seems very interesting –Bu juda qiziq ko'rinadi.
- He probably got a cold –Balki u shamollab qolgan.
- Ali feels himself strange –Ali o'zini g'alati his qilayapti.

In these cases, the semantic load falls on verbs instead of noun phrases we can see. In other words, verbs perform an important grammatical function in these sentences.

Also, abstract verbs are often used in English scientific method texts.

- Many houses were built in short term –Ko'pgina uylar qisqa mudatda qurilgan
- Some new planets were discovered in mid of 2000's –2000-yillarda bir qancha sayyoralar kashf qilangan.

As can be seen in the above examples, the abstract nouns in English are also widely used in the language and the main burden is focused on verbs, i.e. passive relative verbs.

Another interesting aspect of the research is that in today's linguistics, English in the language, the percentage of the use of present tense verbs is equal to past tense verbs, which of course depends on the context of the scientific text.

In general, a scientific text must have a clear statement of logic, and this is its correct and high-quality translation of logic is one of the most important tasks of a translator. Texts in the scientific style often have a uniform appearance, and these texts have expressive features. Interrogative sentences are rarely used in such texts, and even if they are used, they are aimed at drawing the attention of the reader who is familiar with the text. One of the characteristics of scientific texts is that they do not use emotional expressions.

General theory of translation.

The general theory of translation is derived from the concrete experience of translation systematizes conclusions and creates a basis for it. In the process of translation, the results of the translation and their ideas are summarized, and the conditions and factors specific to the translation are taken into account in the translation activity.

The concept of the general theory of translation was developed by the Russian linguist and linguist A.V. Fedorov's works are widely and fully covered. According to this concept, any quality translation text should begin with a philological analysis of its linguistic basis and end with an artistic creation or scientific editing.

A special theory of translation.

A special theory of translation (or, in linguistics, focuses on a pair research on translation) equivalents, variants of correspondence between two languages, as well as factors and criteria for their selection in a specific situation should be taken into account. Within this theory, the main method of studying translation phenomena is the comparison of two languages. For example: Uzbek and Russian, or Russian and English, or English and German.

Transformational theory of translation.

Transformational theory (model) of translation, during translation activity is represented by making changes to the translation text. The reason is that in some cases the meaning of the text cannot be translated completely or it is difficult to translate.

SUMMARY

Not long-ago computers were considered an amazing invention. Today they form part of our everyday lives. The latest thing today is Virtual Reality. A Virtual Reality system can transport the user to exotic locations such as a beach in Hawaii or the inside of human body.

Translation in Uzbek.

O'tgan davrda kompyuterlar ajoyib ixtiro deb hisoblanar edi. Bugungi kunda ular bizning kundalik hayotimizning bir qismini tashkil qiladi. Oxirgi ixtrolardan biri -bu Virtual haqiqat. Virtual haqiqat tizimi foydalanuvchilarni Gavayidagi plyaj yoki inson tanasining ichki qismi kabi ekzotik joylarga olib borish imkoniyatiga ega.

As we can see in the example, the translation from English to Uzbek was not completely translated, but instead underwent a transformation. That is, the meaning of the original text in Uzbek language is clarified with other words.

American linguist N. Chomsky's transformational model of translation related to the ideas of "transformational or generative grammar". Within this theory, the process of creating a translation text is considered as a syntactic transformation of the units and structures of the source language into the units and structures of the translated language, where great attention is paid to the stages and methods of the translation process.

Also, this theory is supported by American translators K. Naide, B.O. It is also mentioned in the works of Kads and V. Koller. In general, the ideas of transformational theory are one of the important enabling methods in translation studies to identify the structures and units that are related to translation and interrelated in the process of translating a pair of languages.

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